

**AREAS OF INCREASING NEED FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES
IN RECENT YEARS****Mansurov Umidjon, Abdullayev Ilhom Khojayorovich**

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

mansurovumidjon@gmail.com

Abstract. In the modern world, information technology plays a leading role in changing the professional environment. Information technology, which has penetrated every field, is changing the way of work, communication methods, and process management. This article covers a major trend in the use of information technology in the workplace and its impact on the professional landscape.

Keywords: information, technology, cyber security, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация. В современном мире информационные технологии играют ведущую роль в изменении профессиональной среды. Информационные технологии, проникшие во все отрасли, меняют способ работы, методы коммуникации и управления процессами. В этой статье рассматриваются основные тенденции использования информационных технологий на рабочем месте и их влияние на профессиональный ландшафт.

Ключевые слова: информация, технологии, кибербезопасность, искусственный интеллект.

INTRODUCTION

In today's society, information technology penetrates various professional fields, providing important competitive advantages in changing work processes, optimizing, increasing productivity, and other aspects. The following are the main directions of their application:

1. The rise of telecommuting:

In recent years, the concept of the workplace has changed radically. With cloud technologies' development and instant messengers' emergence, remote work has opened new horizons for many professionals. Video conferencing and collaboration tools such as Zoom and Slack have broken the mold of traditional office interactions and enabled employees to work effectively from a distance.

The transition to remote work began long before the pandemic, but it was precisely COVID-19 that accelerated this process, forcing companies worldwide to instantly adapt to the new reality. This need has quickly demonstrated the power of remote working, which has had an impact on everything from saving people time and money on the road to increasing productivity and improving work-life balance.

Cloud technology has become one of the foundations of remote work. They not only provide access to specific applications from any device anywhere in the world but also improve data protection with advanced encryption and security measures. Companies are more interested than ever in ensuring not only the availability but also the confidentiality of data.[1]

On the other hand, instant messengers and video conferencing platforms have started to function as virtual meeting rooms and meeting places for the corporate community. Zoom has become a real breakthrough in the field of video communication, providing stable communication even with a large number of participants. Slack solved the problem of informal communication and instant feedback by offering an interface that simulates office interaction.

However, change does not always go smoothly. Questions about confusing time differences in regions, artificially separating work and personal time, and creating an effective remote work culture remain open. Employers must not only provide employees with the necessary tools but also maintain a corporate culture and a sense of belonging to the company's overall goals and objectives. Remote working has already shown its advantages and will remain with us in the future

So remote work is not just a temporary measure. This is a new era in the world of work, opening the doors to global talent and breaking down the old boundaries of the traditional office space. Adapting to these changes is key to the success of every prospective professional.

2. Big data and analytics:

In today's world, where every click, every transaction, and even social communication on the Internet is becoming a source of information, there is a need for deep analysis of this unlimited information. Big data and analytics have become essential parts of the business, allowing companies to understand trends, understand their customers, and most importantly, make informed decisions.

Big data refers to large amounts of data that cannot be efficiently processed by traditional data processing tools. Gathering information is just the beginning. The most important thing is the ability to extract useful information and turn it into actionable knowledge. Using analytics tools and algorithms that can handle large amounts of data turns raw data into valuable insights.

As such, big data and analytics are changing the business landscape, opening the door to a world where informed decisions are the foundation for sustainability and growth.

3. Automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI):

In the era of digitization, automation with the help of artificial intelligence is becoming an important aspect that determines the competitiveness of companies and the efficiency of their business processes. Artificial intelligence not only helps optimize the time workers spend on repetitive tasks, but also increases the accuracy and speed of performing these tasks, which leads to revolutionary changes in various sectors of the economy[4.5].

For example, in the field of medicine, artificial intelligence analyzes medical images and enables early detection of diseases such as cancer. This not only speeds up the diagnostic process but also significantly increases the chances of successful treatment. Also, in biomedical research, artificial intelligence is used to analyze large volumes of data that accelerate the development of new drugs.

In finance, AI-based automation is done through algorithmic trading and fraud detection. Machine learning systems can analyze financial trends and market data to provide valuable predictions and recommendations that traders use to make decisions. Automating the risk management process also reduces the possibility of financial losses caused by human factors.

In the field of customer service, artificial intelligence envisions the role of virtual assistants who can handle customer requests tirelessly 24/7, ensuring high levels of customer satisfaction. AI-based chatbots can recognize text and speech, and provide personalized responses and help.

Intelligent systems are now able not only to execute given algorithms but also to learn and adapt as they work. Virtual agents analyze past interactions and improve their performance by anticipating customer needs. This opens up new horizons for a personalized approach to marketing and service[3.4].

However, AI-based automation also raises certain issues, including ethics, privacy, and data security. The public is also concerned about the loss of jobs due to the replacement of human labor by machines. In many industries, automated systems with artificial intelligence are no longer a means of increasing productivity - they have become a key driver of innovation and development. As these technologies evolve, and become smarter and more integrated into various aspects of professional work, the impact of their implementation continues to grow.

The study and implementation of artificial intelligence is becoming not only an advantage for business, but also a necessity that will decide the future of companies in the long run. A

balanced approach and responsible use of artificial intelligence will allow enterprises not only to increase efficiency but also to provide valuable, innovative products and services for customers and society.

4. Education and development:

The transition from traditional education to digital platforms has become not only a trend but a necessity. E-learning platforms like Coursera and Udemy are changing the educational landscape by breaking down boundaries and providing mass access to knowledge. In the past, professional development was often limited to resources such as educational institutions or corporate training. Now, thanks to online courses, education has become more inclusive and flexible. These platforms offer a wide range of courses, from programming to philosophy. Students and professionals can study according to their preferences and opportunities, balancing work, life, and studies. This model emphasizes individual attention and self-directed learning, allowing users to choose when and where they learn.

Online courses provide access to world-class instructors and high-quality, state-of-the-art educational programs. However, the risks associated with online education should also be noted. Social interaction and practical experience may be limited. Emphasis should be placed on providing interactivity and hands-on learning through virtual simulations and projects. In terms of professional development, e-learning removes barriers to lifelong learning. Today, a professional can study artificial intelligence or management without leaving the workplace. This creates unlimited opportunities for the growth of the specialist's knowledge and level and maintains competitiveness in the labor market.

It can be said that online learning platforms are an important tool that plays a key role in professional development due to their convenience, flexibility, and the wide range of knowledge provided. In the process of integrating digital educational technologies, there must be a balance between technological convenience and the quality of the educational experience.

5. Cyber security:

At a time when information technology is becoming the backbone of business operations, cybersecurity issues are more relevant and important than ever. The lines between the physical and digital spaces are blurring, and companies from small businesses to the largest corporations are exposed to digital threats that can undermine their operations, reputation, and financial well-being. Investments in cyber security are no longer seen as an additional cost but as an integral part of the IT infrastructure management strategy. Protecting data and systems from malware, phishing, hacking, and other cyber threats is becoming a top priority.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Information technology also raises issues of ethics, security, and data privacy in professional practice, and requires careful development of policies and strategies to address them. There is no doubt that the future will be increasingly connected to information technology innovations, and literacy in this field will be crucial for all professionals in this field.

To fully open the possibilities of information technologies, specialists must constantly update their knowledge and skills, be flexible, and adapt to new tools and platforms. In the future, there is a world in which job changes will continue at a rapid pace, and in this world, information technologies will play the role of not only auxiliary tools but also the main factor determining the structure and nature of professional activity.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, it can be said that information technologies are steadily entering every field of professional activity, destroying traditional boundaries and creating new opportunities. They serve as an important tool for increasing productivity, optimizing work processes, and maintaining a competitive advantage in a rapidly changing world. Information technologies and information systems are a basis for innovation and development in all areas.

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